

The Masquerade Cult and Rituals among the Igbo people of Nigeria

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Masquerade cult is an important institution in Igbo culture. It's origin in Igbo culture is not certain. Masquerade activities are shrouded in secrecy. Members of the cult are only those initiated into it. It is only mature males who are capable of keeping secrets that are initiated into the cult. Those not initiated and women are not associated with masquerades cult; except when they come before the cult to fulfil vows made to the masquerade. Members of the cult are not expected to reveal their secret. Masquerades are believed to be the ancestors (the living dead) who visit to dwell with those left behind within the stipulated season in the culture of the people. Traditionally, masquerade played important roles in the society. Such duties are protecting, policing and blessing the community. During the period masquerade dwell with the community, peace is witnessed. Rituals to the masquerades are important and considered as central to the health, stability and maintaining cordial relationship between the living (humans) and the ancestors (the living dead). The traditional priest preside over the rituals to the masquerades. Participants during the ritual are drawn from members of the cult. Persons who made vows to the masquerade the previous year appear before the priest to fulfil them. However, civilization, urbanization and modernity have impacted much on the masquerade institution.

Date Range: 1500 CE - 2026 CE

Region: Igboland, South East, Nigeria

Region tags: Add the map for me using the map of Southeastern Nigeria

five eastern states of Abia, Anambra, Ebonyi, Enugu and Imo in Nigeria.

Status of Participants:

- ✓ Elite
- ✓ Religious Specialists
- ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Site

Does the ritual take place in an outside setting?

– Yes

↳ Enclosed?

– Yes

Notes: It is only those initiated that participate

↳ Elevated?

– No

Notes: Masquerade activities are done in secret. Women and males not initiated do not participate.

↳ By a body of water?

– No

↳ Near fire (e.g., volcano, lava, human-made fire)?

– No

Notes: Fire is only required for roasting of yam and animals for sacrifice.

↳ In a location considered holy?

– Yes

Notes: There masquerades that are housed in shroves. Some have their shrines in a part of the village square.

↳ Other [Specify]

– N/A

Does the ritual take place in an inside setting?

– Yes

↳ Underground?

– No

↳ Is there an acknowledgment or reference to the elements or materials from which the setting is created? (e.g., wood or stone for a building)

– Yes

Notes: There is a platform beside the shrine. Some are stone and others wood. Some are also done on platform moulded with clay.

Is the ritual carried out in a public place?

– No

Notes: It is done only in the presence of the initiated.

Is the ritual carried out in a private place?

– Yes

Notes: Some attama (traditional priests) have shrines of the masquerades. Also, some individuals have their own masquerades and their shrines in their homes. Such persons can perform private sacrifices; but not in the presence of women and males not initiated.

Is there a specific site or building associated with this ritual?

– Yes

Notes: There are grooves and forests associated with masquerades where rituals are performed. Some huts/buildings in the village square where rituals are performed are also associated with masquerades.

Is the site associated with this ritual considered sacred?

– Yes

Notes: The sites are considered sacred and things that will profane the place are not allowed.

Was the site associated with this ritual created?

– Yes

Notes: The site was created for the purpose of masquerade activities. The site could be groove and or building in a part of the village square.

↳ Was it temporary?

– No

Notes: The site is permanent so far the altar is always serviced with sacrifice or rituals. It is a permanent site.

↳ Was it permanent?

– Yes

Notes: Some of the sites have been in existence for decades. They are created to be permanent sites.

Was the site associated with this ritual found?

– Yes

Notes: The sites are founded for the purposes of ritual.

↳ Through divination:

– Yes

Notes: Divination is essential to Igbo traditional. Therefore, divination may have played an important role in the choice of the site.

↳ Through astronomical observation:

– No

↳ Through myths, legends or literature:

– Yes

Notes: Myths and legends and not literature may have played an essential part in founding the site. In Igbo culture, myths are very important in locating history.

Is the site associated with a metaphysical concept?

– Yes

Notes: The sites are often conceived of as divinely chosen. Once the site is determined, it becomes spiritually energised in order for it to serve the purpose for which it was consecrated.

Is the site representative of another physical or metaphysical space?

– Yes

Notes: The site is both physical and metaphysical.

Is the site oriented to the sun, stars, or other astronomical features?

– No

Notes: Masquerades are not oriented to any astronomical features, therefore the sites are not oriented to any astronomical features.

Does the site have a particular directional orientation (e.g., N, S, E, W)?

– No

Is the site oriented to landforms (e.g., mountains, rivers, coast, etc.)?

– Yes

Notes: Some hills/mountains are associated with the masquerade ritual practices.

Frequency

How often is this ritual performed?

– Yes

Notes: Rituals are performed annually or biennial; depending on the masquerade.

↳ Annually:

– Yes

Notes: Most masquerade rituals are performed annually.

↳ Daily:

– No

↳ Weekly:

– No

↳ Seasonally:

– Yes

Notes: There are usually seasons of the year associated with the celebration of the masquerade cults in several areas of Igboland

↳ Once in an individual's lifetime:

– No

Notes: It is a consistent ritual so long a person lives.

↳ Special events/occasions:

– Yes

Notes: There are special events/occasions when the masquerade rituals hold.

↳ During life cycle events (marriage, birth, death, etc.):

– No

↳ Ad hoc:

– Field Doesn't Know

Is the duration of the ritual unspecified?

– No

Is the duration of the ritual specified? (If so, include the range of duration in hours)

– Yes: 9

Notes: There are no strict rules around the timing of the event. However, on average, a full celebration of the masquerade ritual roughly takes nine hours to perform. This begins from morning and ends before sunset.

Participants

Are there agent(s) involved in this ritual?

def: this includes the enactor(s) of the ritual and/or entity or entities responsible for the efficacy of the ritual

– Yes

Notes: There are agents involved in the ritual. The traditional priest is very important in the ritual process. Without him, no ritual is carried out.

↳ How many agents are involved in this ritual?

– I Don't Know

Notes: The number is not specific

↳ Are agents of specific gender/sex for this ritual?

– Yes

↳ Are they male:

– Yes

Notes: Masquerade rituals are essentially male-affair. It is an abomination for females to act as an agent.

↳ Are they female:

– No

Notes: Any request by female is carried to the shrine through an initiated male.

↳ Are they transgender:

– No

Notes: This will amount to an abomination

↳ Are they non-binary:

– I Don't Know

↳ Are they other:

– No

↳ What is the age range of agents in this ritual?

–Specify: The age range is not specific. They must be of age to be able to keep secret.

↳ Do agents have to have biological distinctiveness for this ritual?

(e.g., twin, born breach, albino, mental illness, hermaphrodite, blind, other disability)

– No

Notes: In the past, biological distinctiveness was maintained but was not pronounced. This is because community do have blood link. Today, modernity and civilization have influenced it.

↳ Do agents have to have a specific social role for this ritual?

(e.g., widow, unmarried, etc.)

– Yes

Notes: The agents have specific roles. The chief traditional priest presides over the rituals and performs responsibility on behalf of other agents

↳ Are agents required to be insiders for this ritual?

– Yes

↳ Are agents initiated?

– Yes

Notes: Those initiated are the only qualified people.

↳ Are agents part of the social group?

– Yes

↳ Other:

– N/A

↳ Are agents required to be outsiders for this ritual?

– No

Notes: The agents cannot be outsiders. Being an insider is a prerequisite for being an agent.

↳ Are agents required to be specialists for this ritual?

– No

Notes: It is not all agents that are specialists. The traditional priest can ask any member of the

masquerade cult to assist in the ritual if the need arise.

↳ Are agents non-specialists for this ritual?

– No

Notes: Not all the agents are non-specialists.

↳ Are there specific prohibitions for agents in this ritual?

(e.g., menstruating women, men of a certain age)

– Marriage status: This is not a must in every Igbo culture

– Age: Mature males who can keep secret

– Gender: Male

– Social caste: Must be a member of masquerade cult

– Religious affiliation or status: Traditional religion

– Physical state (e.g. menstruation, illness): The agents must be healthy to be able to carry out the ritual.

↳ Are there supernatural agents associated with this ritual?

– Yes

↳ Are they deceased humans:

– Yes

↳ Are they ancestors:

– Yes

↳ Are they non-human, organic entities:

– No

↳ Are they abiotic or inorganic entities:

– No

↳ Are they divine/spiritual beings:

– Yes

↳ Are they high gods:

– No

Notes: They are not high God.

↳ Are they mixed divine (high-god)/human beings:

– No

Notes: They are masquerades who represent the ancestors.

↳ Are they transformed/self-cultivated humans:

Definition: humans who have undergone deliberate efforts to change/refine/develop/transform themselves.

– No

↳ Other:

– N/A

– Yes

↳ Are they deceased humans:

– Yes

↳ Are they ancestors:

– Yes

↳ Are they non-human, organic entities:

– No

↳ Are they abiotic or inorganic entities:

– No

↳ Are they divine/spiritual beings:

– Yes

Notes: They are ancestors

↳ Are they high gods:

– No

↳ Are they mixed divine (high-god)/human beings:

– No

Notes: They are ancestors

↳ Are they transformed/self-cultivated humans:

Definition: humans who have undergone deliberate efforts to change/refine/develop/transform themselves.

– No

↳ Other:

– N/A

Are there patient(s) involved in this ritual?

Definition: recipient, beneficiary, client, target, victim of ritual

– No

Notes: Patients are not involved in this ritual.

Are there participants other than the agent involved in this ritual?

Definition: besides the agent, other actively participating in ritual, by responding, singing, dancing, interacting with ritual agents

– Yes

↳ How many participants are involved in this ritual?

– N/A

Notes: The number of participants are not specific.

↳ The participants' gender/sex is:

– Yes

Notes: Participates are male gender. Females are not associated with masquerades in Igbo culture.

↳ Male:

– Yes

↳ Female:

– No

↳ Transgender:

– No

↳ Non-binary:

– No

↳ Other:

– N/A

Notes: Only adult males are associated with masquerades.

↳ What is the age range of participants in this ritual?

– Specify: It is from age that one will be able to keep secret.

↳ Do participants have a specific social role for this ritual?

– No

Notes: Every participate does not have specific roles. Some are spectators.

↳ Are participants required to be insiders for this ritual?

– Yes

Notes: Every participant is an initiate. Therefore, they are all insiders.

↳ Are participants required to be outsiders for this ritual?

– No

Notes: Outsiders are not required. Masquerade activities are for only the initiates. Outsiders have the privilege to see the masquerades only when the masquerade is moving around in the community. They come out only to watch the masquerade.

↳ Are participants required to be specialists for this ritual?

– No

Notes: It is not every participant that is required to be a specialist. Some participants are specialists while some are not.

↳ Are participants non-specialists for this ritual?

– No

Notes: Just as I have noted. Some participants are required to be specialists, while some are non-specialists.

↳ Are there specific prohibitions for participants to take part in this ritual?

– Yes [specify]: There are specific prohibition. For instance, anyone being initiated into the masquerade cult is not expected to shout or cry. If it happens the person will be disqualified.

↳ Are there supernatural beings that act as participants in this ritual?

– Yes

Notes: Yes. The masquerade is seen as supernatural being and being an important participant means that it acts as supernatural being during the ritual.

↳ Are they deceased humans:

– Yes

Notes: They are deceased humans.

↳ Are they ancestors:

– Yes

↳ Are they non-human, organic entities:

– No

↳ Are they abiotic or inorganic entities:

– No

↳ Are they divine/spiritual beings

– Yes

Notes: Masquerades are the spiritual beings that participate in the ritual.

↳ Are they high gods:

– No

↳ Are they mixed divine (high-god)/human beings:

– No

Notes: The researcher does not know.

↳ Are they transformed/self-cultivated humans:

– No

↳ Others:

– No

Are there spectators in this ritual?

Definition: not actively participating in ritual or required to perform any actions

– No

Notes: The participants in the masquerade ritual are all initiates and are seen as participants.

Cause/Trigger

Is this ritual practiced at will?

– No

Notes: The ritual has specific period calculated based on the traditional calendar.

Is participation obligatory?

– Yes

Notes: Those required to be part of the ritual celebration must as a matter of necessity attend the masquerade ritual celebration.

↳ Consequences of non-participation:

– Yes

↳ Social ostracism

– No

Notes: They may not necessarily face ostracism but this may happen in some instances.

↳ Status loss

– Yes

Notes: Some individuals lose their status when they fail to take their place in the celebration of the masquerade rituals in their family or clan as such positions would be taken by another.

↳ Material/Physical punishment

– Yes

Notes: Sometimes, material or physical loss is suffered by men who abandon their roles in the celebration of the masquerade rituals of their family or clan.

↳ Supernatural punishment

– Yes

Notes: The people hold that supernatural punishment may follow those who refuse to play

their part in the celebration of masquerade ritual in their families or clans.

↳ Other
– N/A

Is this ritual practiced as part of an event?

– Yes

Notes: Ritual is part of activities during masquerade festival.

Is this ritual practiced as part of calendric or astrological causes/events?

– Yes

Notes: There is a time within the traditional calendar when it is done. It is the responsibility of someone with the knowledge of how to calculate the calendar to do it.

Is this ritual triggered by hemerological considerations (system of favorable/unfavorable days)?

– No

Is the ritual practiced in response to seasonal change?

– No

Is the ritual practiced in response to specific natural events (e.g., drought, ecological death, etc.)?

– No

Is the ritual practiced in response to specific social events (e.g., death of a leader, etc.)?

– Yes

Notes: The death of someone can make masquerade to appear; especially during the funeral. Some of the masquerades cannot appear in such events without performing rituals.

Is the ritual performed in reaction to an ominous event?

– No

Notes: Masquerade rituals take place as scheduled and are not in response to any event outside of their natural timing.

Is this ritual practiced during a specific life stage?

– No

Is this ritual part of another ritual?

– No

Notes: The ritual is sufficient enough that it does not depend on another ritual to be efficient and effective.

Is this ritual financially sponsored by non-participants?

– No

Purpose

Is the purpose of this ritual for maintenance?

– Yes

Notes: The living also try to maintain cordial relationship with the living dead (ancestors). Masquerades are believed to be the ancestors, therefore the ritual is majorly to maintain cordial relationship with the ancestors.

Is the purpose of the ritual to cause a change?

– Yes

↳ Is the change expected to be positive:

– Yes

Notes: The family observes the ritual to keep a cordial relationship with the ancestors. When the rituals are conducted in the prescribed manner, it results in positive actions of benevolence, blessings and care from the ancestors.

↳ Is the change expected to be negative:

– No

↳ Is the change expected to be neutral:

– No

↳ Select the type of change:

– Political

– Legal

– Social

– Cultural

– Spiritual

– Ecological

Notes: The ritual is to ensure peace that will positively reflect on every aspect of the community.

What is the domain involved in this ritual?

– Yes

Notes: It is every village/community that conduct their own ritual. What happens in one community is not is regulated or determined by another community.

↳ Is it divine/spiritual:

– Yes

Notes: The ritual is viewed as having divine/spiritual significance.

↳ Is it non-human organic entities (e.g., nature, animals, plants):

– No

↳ Is it abiotic/inorganic entities (and objects):

– No

↳ Is it ecological:

– No

↳ Is it transformed humans:

– Yes

Notes: The ancestors whom the family consults during the ritual celebration are transformed humans who now occupy another realm of existence in the terrestrial world.

↳ Is it for knowledge transmission (e.g., oral storytelling):

– No

↳ Other:

– N/A

Is there a specific goal(s) associated with this ritual?

– Yes

↳ Is devotion a goal of the ritual?

– Yes

Notes: The ritual confirms the devotion of the living members of family/clan with the ancestors.

↳ For deceased humans:

– Yes

↳ For ancestors:

– Yes

↳ For non-human, organic entities:

– No

↳ For abiotic or inorganic entities:

– No

↳ For divine/spiritual beings:

– Yes

Notes: The rituals are celebrated to keep the human members of the family in constant communion with the living dead/ancestors.

↳ Are they high gods:

– No

↳ Are they mixed divine (high-god)/human beings:

– Yes

Notes: The ancestors who are consulted by the Igbo people in their masquerade rituals are not high gods. Rather they are transformed humans. They have crossed the realm of the living and now occupy a special position in-between those occupied by humans and the high god. They are transformed humans who are now viewed as possessing some extra-human powers.

↳ For transformed/self-cultivated humans:

– No

↳ Other:

– N/A

↳ Is creation of a cultural product a goal of this ritual?

– No

↳ Is propitiation a goal of this ritual?

– Yes

Notes: The people use the opportunity of this ritual contact with the ancestors to make propitiation for their errors and inadequacies.

↳ Is domestication of agents a goal?

Definition: temporary or permanent transformation of an inimical or indifferent target into something beneficial for practitioners.

– No

↳ Is this ritual practiced to gain information?

– Yes

Notes: Since the ancestors are believed to possess supernatural powers, they are believed to be in possession of information that are not known by humans. Seeking them and appeasing them bring humans to a place where they obtain useful information that would help them in their journeys of life.

↳ About the future/past/present:

– Yes

↳ General information:

– Yes

↳ About something specific:

– No

↳ Is this ritual practiced for cosmic maintenance?

– Yes

Notes: The ritual maintains a balance between the human population and their departed fore bears. It serves as a means of uniting the living with their dead/departed ancestors who are seen as holding important positions in their affairs.

↳ Is this ritual practiced for ecological maintenance and/or stewardship?

– Yes

↳ To increase felt connection with the more-than-human world:

– Yes

↳ To acknowledge responsibility for environmental harm:

– No

↳ To channel shame into collective reparative action:

– No

↳ To try to influence a larger change in the community (e.g., environmental values, motivations, beliefs, emotions):

– No

↳ To evoke moral outrage (towards ecological injustice):

– No

↳ Is this ritual practiced for self-transformation?

– Yes

Notes: In a sense, the ritual has the capacity to support the transformation of individuals to align themselves to the standards of the ancestors.

↳ To become god-like:

– No

↳ To become immortal:

– No

Notes: The Igbo people do not hold the view of human immortality.

↳ To achieve divine or superhuman attributes:

– No

↳ For salvation/liberation from the world:

– Yes

Notes: The form of salvation/liberation achieved by those who follow the masquerade

rituals among the Igbo is such that focuses on salvation from evil forces which humans cannot overcome by themselves but by the help and support of the ancestors and other supernatural powers.

↳ For spiritual cleansing:
– Yes

↳ To achieve moral perfection:
– No

↳ For an initiation into a new status:
– Yes

↳ To achieve a change in mental state:
– No

↳ Is this ritual practiced as a way to express gratitude to a god or other supernatural agents?
– Yes

Notes: Libations are poured out to the ancestors to express gratitude to them and to also seek their protection from all evil.

↳ Is this ritual performed for purification?
– Yes

Notes: One core aspect of this ritual is the submission of individuals for purification by the ancestors so the the latter could continue to provide guidance and support to the human members of the family.

↳ Is it physical:
– Yes

↳ Is it mental:

– No

↳ Is it emotional:

– Yes

↳ Other:

– N/A

↳ Is this ritual practiced for exorcism purposes?

– No

↳ Is this ritual practiced for health/healing purposes?

– Yes

Notes: The ritual is practised for many reasons among which is the healing of physical, emotional, material, financial etc of the human members of the family. It is also observed to allow barren members of the family receive the favour of the ancestors to have children.

↳ During a specific illness?

– No

↳ During an injury?

– No

↳ To improve fertility?

– Yes

↳ To achieve longevity?

– Yes

↳ To support development/growth?

– Yes

↳ To achieve vitality?

– Yes

↳ To improve virility?

– Yes

↳ To achieve resurrection?

– No

Notes: The idea of resurrection is not known to Igbo tradition

↳ Is this ritual practiced to transmit information?

– Yes

Notes: The ancestors use the opportunity of the ritual to communicate with the living members of their family or clan. The living also use the opportunity to pour out their desires and fears to the ancestors.

↳ Is this ritual practiced to obtain luck (generic)?

– Yes

Notes: It is observed to obtain the favour of the ancestors. This favour may sometimes appear in the form of luck experienced by the members of the family.

↳ Is this a naming ritual?

– No

↳ Is this ritual practiced to improve the community's modes of subsistence?

– Yes

Notes: When faithfully observed, the ritual is believed to have the power to improve the living conditions of the family/clan. This includes increased rainfall, bounteous harvest, safety in the fields and on journeys, safe travels among others.

↳ To increase the amount of rain for agricultural/horticultural productivity:
– Yes

↳ For crop success:
– Yes

↳ For livestock success:
– Yes

↳ For success in gathering:
– Yes

↳ For success in fishing:
– Yes

↳ For success in hunting:
– Yes

↳ For industrial productivity:
– Yes

↳ For success in commerce/mercantilism/market exchange:
– Yes

↳ Is this ritual practiced to induce harm?
– No

Notes: Harm is not a focus of this ritual celebration.

↳ Is this ritual practiced for protection purposes?
– Yes

Notes: The living members of the family/clan use the occasion of the ritual celebration to request the ancestors' protection from harm and other evil forces.

↳ Against spells/witchcraft:
– Yes

↳ To avoid illness:
– Yes

↳ To avoid injury:
– Yes

↳ For a safe pregnancy:
– Yes

↳ For children:
– Yes

↳ To avoid discovery:
– No

↳ Against weapons:
– Yes

↳ To avoid vices (temptation):
– Yes

↳ Is this ritual associated with warfare or ritual contests (e.g., stick ball games)?
– No

↳ Is this ritual associated with craft practices (e.g., weaving, etc.)?

– No

↳ Is this ritual associated with infanticide?

– No

↳ Is this ritual associated with gambling/games of chance?

– No

↳ Is this ritual associated with travel?

– No

↳ Is this ritual associated with social relations?

– Yes

Notes: The ritual celebration has an indirect consequence of fostering the social relations among the extended family members and among clans in Igboland.

↳ As part of a celebration:

– Yes

↳ For love:

– No

↳ For social coordination:

– Yes

↳ To reduce social discord:

– Yes

↳ To maintain partner faithfulness:

– No

↳ To cause religious conversion:

– No

↳ To obtain subjugation/control:

– No

↳ Is this ritual practiced to obtain wealth or success?

– No

Notes: Wealth or success are not the primary focus. However, sometimes, they are inevitable consequences of the observance of the ritual.

Is the causal efficacy assessed?

– Yes

↳ Concrete outcomes in the world:

– Yes

↳ Further ritual checks:

– Yes

↳ Other:

–Specify: If the community witnesses peace and tranquility, it is believed that the ritual was efficacious.

Techniques

Is sound practiced during this ritual?

– Yes

Notes: Iron or wooden gong can be sounded during ritual.

Is it considered "music" in the local culture/community?

– Yes

Is this sound coordinated with movement?

– Yes

↳ Is it oral?

– Yes

↳ Is it communal? (e.g., choir)

– No

Notes: This is observed at the family level but sometimes, it is done at the level of the clan.

↳ Is it individual?

– No

↳ Is there a call and response?

– Yes

Notes: The priest of the masquerade cult makes a call at specific points during the ritual and it is the responsibility of those present to respond.

↳ It involves singing:

– Yes

Notes: Singing is an integral part of the ritual

↳ It involves chanting:

– Yes

Notes: There are lots of chanting done during the ritual. This is an accepted way of communicating with the ancestors who are at the core of the masquerade cult.

↳ it involves invocation/prayer:

– Yes

Notes: Prayers are made to the spirits of the ancestors during the ritual.

↳ It involves mantras:

– Yes

↳ It involves wailing/cheering (heightened emotional expression):

– No

↳ It involves narrative/recitation:

– Yes

Notes: There are recitations of potent words during the ritual. These words are believed to have specific purposes in the ritual process.

↳ It involves whistling:

– I Don't Know

↳ It involves shouting/loud vocalizations:

– No

↳ Is the sound produced with parts of the body?

– Yes

Notes: Sounds are made with sacred objects as well as those made verbally for specific purposes during the ritual process.

↳ Does the sound involve hand movement?

– Yes

↳ Does it involve clapping?

– No

↳ Does it involve body concussion?

– No

↳ Does the sound involve feet movement?

– Yes

↳ How many individuals are involved in producing the sound:

– Yes

Notes: The number is not specific.

↳ Is the sound/movement scripted?

– No

Notes: The sounds/movements are not scripted. They are preserved in oral form.

↳ Is the sounds/movement semantic?

– Yes

Notes: Some of the she sounds are produced verbally.

↳ Is the sounds/movement mimetic (of non-human animal, natural, human)?

– No

↳ Is this sound/movement restricted to ritual use?

– Yes

Notes: Some of the sounds produced during the ritual are restricted to the rituals alone. They are held as sacred sounds which are not produced in everyday life.

↳ Is the sound/movement carried out by specialists?

– No

↳ Does it require formal training?

– No

↳ Does the sound/movement change throughout the ritual?

– Yes

↳ Is the change correlated to the stage of the ritual?

– Yes

↳ Is there musical texture in the sound?

– Yes

↳ Is it homophonic:

– Yes

↳ Is it monophonic:

– Yes

Notes: Sometimes during the ritual, sounds are produced using a single melodic line or performed by just one individual.

↳ Is it polyphonic:

– No

↳ Is it heterophonic:

– Yes

Notes: This may happen during some ritual performances although not deliberately in some cases. It could be as a result of the singers not starting each line of the song at the same time or when they are meters apart during ritual process making each sound travel few seconds apart from each other.

↳ Is it biphonic:

– No

– Yes

↳ Is it homophonic:
– Yes

↳ Is it monophonic:
– Yes

↳ Is it polyphonic:
– No

↳ Is it heterophonic:
– No

↳ Is it biphonic:
– No

↳ Is the sound regulated by pitch?
– No

↳ Is the sound regulated by rhythm?
– No

↳ Is the sound considered central to the ritual?
– Yes

↳ The sound is:
– Improvised

↳ Does the sound involve conscious agency?

– Yes

↳ Are there instruments/objects involved in creating sounds for the ritual?

– Yes

↳ Are they membranophone:

Definition: Instruments that produce sound by vibrating a membrane (e.g., kettle drums, cylindrical drums).

– Yes

Notes: Some of the objects used in sound production during the ritual include gongs, sacred wooden object, local bell-like objects etc

↳ Are they idiophone:

Definition: Instruments that create sound through vibrating themselves (e.g., xylophones, jaw's harp).

– Yes

Notes: Some of the objects used in sound production during the ritual include gongs, sacred wooden object, local bell-like objects etc which produce sounds through the vibration of their parts

↳ Are they aerophone:

Definition: Instruments that create noise by pushing vibrating columns of air through them (e.g., accordions, pitch pipes, ocarinas, bagpipes).

– No

↳ Are they chordophone:

Definition: Instruments that produce sound by vibrating strings (e.g., guitar, violin, harp).

– No

Notes: Chorded instruments are not used during this ritual process

↳ Are they electrophone:

Definition: Instruments where the sound is produced by electric or electronic means (e.g., synthesizers, computers).

– No

Notes: Electrophone instruments are not used in this ritual celebration.

↳ Are they architectural features:

def: water channeled in underground canals, fountains, or other architectural features that create sounds for the ritual

– No

↳ How many individuals are involved in producing these instrumental sounds:

– Yes

Notes: At least one individual is usually involved in sound production during the ritual. Each family size determines how small or large the group would be

↳ Is it scripted?

– No

Notes: Sounds produced during the masquerade ritual in Igboland are not usually scripted.

↳ Is it semantic?

– No

Notes: The sounds are usually orally preserved.

↳ Is it mimetic (of non-human animal, natural, human)?

– No

↳ Is it restricted to ritual use?

– Yes

Notes: In many cases, the sounds are restricted for ritual use

↳ Is it performed by specialists?

– Yes

Notes: In a sense, only initiated male members of the family/clan take part in masquerade rituals in Igboland. To this extent, they may be considered specialists in some sense. So the sounds are performed by specialists or at least by trainees undergoing informal specialist course.

↳ Does it require formal training?

– No

Notes: This is not often the case.

↳ Does the sound change throughout the ritual?

– Yes

Notes: The sound changes at some points during the ritual

↳ Does the change correlate to the stage of the ritual?

– Yes

↳ Is there musical texture in the instrumental sound?

– Yes

↳ Is it homophonic:

– Yes

Notes: The sounds produced during the ritual are sometimes homophonic in nature

↳ Is it monophonic:

– Yes

Notes: The sounds produced during the ritual are sometimes monophonic in nature

↳ Is it polyphonic:

– No

Notes: sounds produced during the ritual are not usually polyphonic in nature

↳ Is it heterophonic:
– No

↳ Is it biphonic:
– No

↳ Is the sound regulated by pitch?
– No

↳ Is the sound regulated by rhythm?
– No

↳ Is the sound considered central to the ritual?
– Yes

↳ The sound is:
– Improvised

Is movement involved in this ritual?

– Yes

↳ Is it considered "dance" by the culture that practices this ritual?
– No

↳ Is it coordinated with sound?
– Yes

↳ Does it involve the use of objects?

– Yes

Notes: It involves the use of gongs, bells etc

↳ How many individuals are involved in this movement

– Specify: The number is not specific.

↳ Do actors move in close proximity to each other?

– No

Notes: Actors do not always move in close proximity to each other.

↳ Do actors move towards each other?

– No

↳ Do actors move away from each other?

– Yes

↳ Does it involve ritualized action?

– Yes

Notes: Some ritualised actions take place during the ritual process. These include chants, potent speeches and other actions required for a successful ritual celebration.

↳ It involves kneeling:

– Yes

Notes: The ritual performers genuflect, bend and assume some other physical positions they consider necessary when performing the masquerade ritual in Igboland

↳ It involves prostrating:

– No

↳ Does it involve remaining immobile:

– No

↳ Does it involve artistic movement (e.g., mandala)?

– No

↳ Is it mimetic (natural, non-human world)?

– No

↳ Does it involve a symbolic representation?

– No

↳ Does it include stereotyped/stylized movements?

– No

↳ Does it involve a procession?

– No

↳ Does it involve a pilgrimage?

– Yes

↳ What is the distance covered (in kilometers)?

– N/A

↳ Are there gestures involved in the movement?

– Yes

↳ Are there particular postures involved in the movement?

– No

↳ Is there a specific proximity considered between individuals while moving?

– No

Is there regalia/ornamentation used as part of this ritual?

– Yes

Notes: Masquerades are dressed in clothes which cover their entire body from the crown of the head to the sole of the feet. They are not meant to be seen as they are representatives of deceased members of the family/clan. Therefore, their clothing/regalia are special attires for the ritual.

↳ Are there specific body markings done for the ritual?

– No

Notes: They are covered from head to toe so even if they had body markings, it will be difficult or impossible to see them under their regalia.

↳ Is there hair regulation as part of this ritual?

– No

↳ Is there tooth modification involved in this ritual?

– No

↳ Are individuals partly or fully naked as part of this ritual?

– No

↳ Are scars made as part of this ritual?

– No

↳ Are piercings made as part of this ritual?

– No

↳ Does genital modification take place during this ritual?

– No

↳ Do individuals have to wear specific clothing for this ritual?

– Yes

Notes: They wear masquerade attire or regalia as it is required of participants.

↳ Are there specific shoes to be worn for this ritual?

– No

↳ Is there a head covering used during the ritual?

– Yes

Notes: Masks are used by the masquerades all through the period of the rituals.

↳ Is it removed at some point during the ritual?

– No

↳ Is it added during the ritual?

– No

Notes: It is worn before the commencement of the ritual

↳ Are the clothing colors regulated for the ritual?

– I Don't Know

↳ Are there specific clothing items restricted for exclusive use in the ritual?

– Yes

Notes: The masquerade regalia are restricted to the rituals or masquerade rituals in general.

↳ Are there jewelry/charms used during this ritual?

– No

↳ Are masks used during the ritual?

– Yes

Are there materials/objects used in this ritual?

– Yes

↳ Are they totems:

– No

Notes: Items depend on the family or clan tradition.

↳ Are they religious icons:

– No

↳ Are they fetishes:

– No

↳ Are they vessels:

– Yes

↳ Are they masks:

– Yes

Notes: Masquerades in Igboland wear masks which conceal their identity because they are conceived of as ancestors who have departed the world, hence humans are not meant to know their true identity.

↳ Are they standards (banner, flag):

– Yes

↳ Other:

–Specify: Certain objects from the Palm tree are used during the ritual.

↳ How are these materials/objects implemented?

– Yes

↳ Are they sound-producing:

– Yes

Notes: But not all of them.

↳ Are they divination tools:

– No

↳ Are they drug paraphernalia:

– No

Notes: The ritual is not associated with drugs use.

↳ Are they cutting devices:

– Yes

↳ Are they sceptres/wands:

– No

↳ Is text used during this ritual?

– No

↳ Is painting used during the ritual?

– Yes

↳ Is a technological object used in this ritual?

– No

↳ Are plants or plant parts used in this ritual?

– Yes

Notes: Plant parts like leaves, palm fronts and palm nuts are associated with the ritual

↳ Are animals or animal parts used in this ritual?

– Yes

Notes: Animals are used for sacrifices during the ritual

↳ Are human body parts (including flesh) used in this ritual?

– No

Notes: Some members of the culture believe that some masquerades received human ritual in the past.

↳ Are bodily fluids used as part of this ritual?

– Yes

↳ Are they human:

– No

↳ Are they non-human:

– Yes

↳ Do topical applications take place during this ritual?

– No

↳ Is water used?

– Yes

↳ Is earth used?

– Yes

↳ Is a mirror used?

– Yes

Notes: This is however the influence of civilization on the masquerade institution.

↳ Are textiles used?

– Yes

↳ Is fire used?

– Yes

↳ Is it smoke:

– Yes

↳ Is it incense:

– No

↳ Is it candle(s):

– No

↳ Is it torch(es):

– No

↳ Is it burnt objects like paper, leaves, or wood:

– No

↳ Is it a large fire:

– No

Notes: The use of fire depends on the family or clan tradition and what the fire symbolises in their individual tradition.

↳ Is there interaction with ritual material during the ritual?

– Yes

↳ Is it passed around?

– Yes

↳ Is it kissed?

– Yes

↳ Is it placed somewhere specifically?

– Yes

↳ Is it processed to create something else?

– No

↳ Is it touched?

– Yes

↳ Is it used to touch?

– I Don't Know

↳ Is it altered during the course of the ritual?

– No

↳ Is it worn?

– No

↳ Is it used to maintain a boundary?

– No

↳ Is it placed at a specific physical distance?

– Yes

↳ Is it close?

– Yes

↳ Is it far?

– No

Does consumption take place as part of this ritual?

– Yes

↳ How many individuals participate in consumption?

– N/A

↳ Is food consumed?

– Yes

↳ Is it human:

Definition: this can include by fire, natural features of landscape

– No

↳ Is it a non-human animal:

– Yes

Notes: Animals are sacrificed during the ritual. Apart from the sacrificial animals, some other animals are also killed for consumption during the ritual celebration.

↳ Is it a plant:

– No

↳ Is it a fungus:

– No

↳ Is this food restricted to the ritual?

– Yes

↳ Is the preparation of the food ritualized?

– Yes

↳ Is the presentation of the food ritualized?

– Yes

↳ In what state is the food consumed?

– Cooked

↳ Is a non-normative portion (excessive or deficient) served?

– No

↳ Is it sacralized food?

– Yes

↳ Is it symbolic food?

e.g., standing in for another food or substance or metaphysical concept

– Yes

↳ Is the food consumed associated with healing powers?

– No

↳ Does food consumption happen on site?

– Yes

↳ Does the food consumption happen off site?

– No

↳ Does the ritual take place before food consumption?

– Yes

↳ Is there an acknowledgement of the supernatural source of the food?

– Yes

Notes: The Igbo believe that good harvest is made possible by the supernatural being and so they believe that for the food prepared to have made it harvest time and now being cooked, it is an act of the divine powers

↳ Is there an acknowledgement of the environmental source of the food?

– Yes

↳ Is there an acknowledgement of the (human) provider of the food?

– Yes

↳ Does the ritual encourage sustainable eating behavior?

– I Don't Know

↳ Are there specific types of consumption that are forbidden?

– Yes

↳ Is a psychoactive substance used in this ritual?

– No

↳ How is the substance used in this ritual?

– No

Notes: Psychoactive substances are not used in the ritual

↳ Are other substances used in this ritual?

– Yes

↳ Are they charms:

– No

↳ Are they inorganic minerals:

– Yes

↳ Is the substance shared from a communal vessel or implement?

– Yes

Does the ritual stimulate an altered state of consciousness?

– No

Are offerings involved as part of this ritual?

– Yes

↳ Are the offerings non-material?

– Yes

↳ Are the offerings material?

– Yes

↳ Are they consumed by the ritual participants?

– Yes

↳ Are the offerings symbolic?

– No

↳ Do offerings serve as payments for the ritual specialists?

– Yes

Notes: Although the community members do not understand it like that.

↳ Are animals offered?

– Yes

↳ Is the whole animal offered?

– Yes

↳ How many animals are offered?

– N/A

↳ Is part of the animal offered?

– Yes

↳ How many parts of the animals are offered?

– N/A

↳ Are the animals domestic?

– Yes

↳ How many domestic?

– N/A

↳ Are they wild animals?

– No

↳ Are humans offered?

– No

- ↳ Is food offered for this ritual?
– Yes
- ↳ Are specific drinks offered for this ritual?
– Yes
- ↳ Are psychoactive substances offered?
– No
- ↳ Are commodities offered?
– Yes
- ↳ Are household items offered?
– Yes
- ↳ Are personal items offered?
– Yes
- ↳ Is clothing offered?
– Yes
- ↳ Are musical instrument offered?
– No
- ↳ Are texts offered?
– No
- ↳ Are weapons offered?
– No

↳ Is money (or other valuable items) offered?

– Yes

↳ Are precious substances offered?

– Yes

↳ Other:

– Specify: What people offer is a function of the promises made to the masquerade the previous year/years.

Are non-normative practices involved in this ritual?

– Yes

↳ Are they self-imposed?

– No

↳ Are they other-imposed?

– No

↳ Does it involve fasting?

– Yes

↳ Is it complete:

– Yes

↳ Is it partial:

– No

↳ Is it for a determinate duration:

– I Don't Know

↳ Is it for an indeterminate duration:

– I Don't Know

↳ Does it involve sensory deprivation?

– No

↳ Does it involve submersion in water?

– No

↳ Does it involve being in a difficult bodily position?

– No

↳ Does it involve the consumption of disgusting substances?

– No

↳ Does it involve sleep deprivation?

– Yes

↳ Does it involve physical exhaustion?

– Yes

↳ Does it involve physical discomfort?

– Yes

↳ Is it environmental:

– Yes

↳ Is it a discomfort due to specific clothing:

– No

↳ Is it a surface discomfort:
– Yes

↳ Does it involve excessive labor?
– No

↳ Does it involve psychological discomfort?
– No

↳ Does it involve physical pain?
– Yes

↳ It involves piercing(s):
– Yes

↳ It involves fire:
– No

↳ It involves beating:
– Yes

↳ It involves flagellation:
– No

↳ It involves cutting:
– Yes

↳ It involves abrasion:
– No

↳ Does it involve the consumption of painful substances:

– No

↳ Does it involve positive emotion?

– Yes

↳ It involves ecstasy:

– Yes

↳ It involves joy:

– Yes

↳ It involves love:

– No

↳ It involves feelings of connection:

– Yes

↳ It involves pride:

– Yes

↳ It involves hope:

– Yes

↳ It involves gratitude:

– Yes

↳ It involves awe:

– Yes

↳ It involves compassion/empathy:

– I Don't Know

↳ It involves equanimity:

– Yes

↳ Other:

– N/A

↳ Does it involve negative emotion?

– No

↳ Does it involve breath manipulation?

– No

↳ Does it involve a vow of silence?

– Yes

↳ Does it involve the subversion of social categories?

– I Don't Know

↳ Does it involve non-normative sexual acts?

– No

↳ Does it involve celibacy?

– No

Formal Features

Does the ritual stand by itself?

– Yes

Notes: The ritual is an independent ceremony in Igboland. It has its cult distinct from others while its processes are unique and directed to the ancestors.

Is the ritual part of a sequence of rituals?

– No

Notes: The ritual stands alone and is distinct in practice and observance.

Is the repetition of the ritual determinate (e.g., an action must be repeated a certain number of times)?

– Yes

Is the repetition of the ritual non-determinate?

– Yes

Compared to everyday non-ritual behavior, what is the level of repetition?

– Medium

Notes: It is determined by the officiating priest.

Compared to everyday non-ritual behavior, what is the level of rigidity of this ritual?

– High

Notes: It is a ritual that is believed to be important for the future survival of the community.

Compared to everyday non-ritual activity, what is the level of arousal of this ritual?

– High

Compared to everyday non-ritual activity, what is the level of physical activity in this ritual?

– High

Is there behavioral conformity?

– Yes

- ↳ What is the level of behavioral conformity
 - High

Is there synchrony in this ritual?

– No

Is there entrainment in this ritual?

– Yes

- ↳ What is the level of entrainment?
 - High

- ↳ Is there movement/sound/attention?
 - Yes

- ↳ Is the entrainment emerging endogenously between participants in the ritual?
(e.g., clapping, chanting without external stimulus)
 - Yes

- ↳ Is the entrainment to an external stimulus?
(e.g., a ritual leader, a musical beat)
 - No

- ↳ Does the entrainment induce emotional conformity?
 - No

Is there coordination in this ritual?

– Yes

- ↳ What is the level of coordination?

– High

↳ Is there movement/sound/attention?

– Yes

Is there preparation time needed to carry out this ritual?

– Yes

How many hours are involved in the ritual preparation?

– N/A

Notes: There is no specific hours. Rituals end whenever the participants think that they are done with what they are expected to do.

Are there preparation activities involved?

– Yes

↳ Does it involve fasting:

– Yes

↳ Does it involve purification:

– Yes

Notes: Those to be involved in the rituals are expected to be ritually pure as the ancestors require.

↳ Does it involve learning/training:

– Yes

Notes: It involves informal learning through observations and interactions with ritual specialists.

↳ Does it involve penance:

– No

↳ Does it involve abstention:

– No

Is practice/expertise required to carry out this ritual?

– Yes

Notes: The masquerades have priest who is the chief officiating priest.

What is the level of expertise required?

– High

What is the level of economic cost involved to practice this ritual?

– Yes

↳ In local currency:

– N/A

Notes: The cost incurred during this ritual celebration depends on so many factors. These include the financial capacity of the family and clan, the statutory needs of the ritual celebration etc

↳ Number of people or days of labor equivalent:

– Specify: Not specified

Notes: The number is not specified. It depends on what can be achieved and the hours available to those saddled with the preparatory steps required to hold a successful ritual celebration.

↳ Other measure of cost:

– Specify: Sometimes it depends on the vow a person made the previous year.

– Yes

↳ In local currency:

– N/A

Notes: This is a factor of the financial capacity of the family or clan. They could get the basic

minimum ritual materials or buy elaborate materials as they are able to afford.

↳ **Number of people or days of labor equivalent:**

– Specify: Not specified

Notes: Number of people and days of labour are not specified. They depend on the number of individuals available and the the time they have got to work at preparation for the ritual celebration.

↳ **Other measure of cost:**

– Specify: Depends on vow sometimes.

Notes: Sometimes it depends on the vow someone made the previous year.

What is the transmission mode of the ritual?

– Other: There is no specific mode

Notes: Spiritual knowledge is passed on from the elderly members of the family to the younger ones who replace them as participants in the ritual in subsequent years.

How is the ritual transmitted?

– In oral form

Who or what has authority over this ritual?

– Divine beings

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